

COVID-19 Bibliometrics 30th November 2020 – 6th December 2020

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A. Medicine and Health

December 4, 2020 (Nat Commun)

Longitudinal symptom dynamics of COVID-19 infection

Mizrahi, B., Shilo, S., Rossman, H. *et al*

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-020-20053-y>

The authors extracted data from primary-care electronic health records and nationwide distributed surveys to assess the longitudinal dynamics of symptoms before and throughout SARS-CoV-2 infection to better understand the full clinical spectrum of symptoms experienced by adults and children infected with COVID-19.

December 3, 2020 (Mayo Clinic Proceedings)

COVID-19: Understanding Inter-Individual Variability and Implications for Precision Medicine

Naveen L. Pereira, Ferhaan Ahmad, Mirnela Byku *et al*.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mayocp.2020.11.024>

There are demographic characteristics such as age, race, and ethnicity, and sex and biological differences such as ACE2 expression, immune regulation, and genetics that define the well-known variability in COVID-19 disease manifestation, susceptibility, and progression. Identifying and validating these individual differences and leveraging digital platforms including the use of artificial intelligence in developing predictive algorithms may help in individualizing targeted therapy and hospitalization and assist in the logistics of vaccine administration.

December 2, 2020 (Singapore Medical Journal)

A review of COVID-19-related thrombosis and anticoagulation strategies specific to the Asian population

Kai Chin Poh, Victoria Yu Jia Tay, Sarah Huixin Lin *et al*.

<https://doi.org/10.11622/smedj.2020174>

Severe COVID-19 is widely regarded as a risk factor for venous thromboembolism. This review article aimed to summarise the current understanding of arteriovenous thromboembolic complications in COVID-19 and discuss management strategies for prevention and treatment of thrombotic events in Asian COVID-19 patients.

December 2, 2020 (Diagn Interv Radiol)

Predictive value of CT imaging findings in COVID-19 pneumonia at the time of first-screen regarding the need for hospitalization or intensive care unit

Tekcan Sanli DE, Yildirim D, Sanli AN, et al.

<https://doi.org/10.5152/dir.2020.20421>

In this study, the authors aimed to reveal the relationship between initial lung parenchymal involvement patterns and the subsequent need for hospitalization and/or intensive care unit admission in COVID-19 positive cases. They found that in the case of infiltration dominated by a right middle or upper lobe involvement with a consolidation pattern, there is a higher risk of future intensive care need. Also, the need for intensive care increases as the number of affected lobes and the percentage of affected parenchymal involvement increase.

December 1, 2020 (JAMA Int. Med)

Seroprevalence of Antibodies to SARS-CoV-2 in 10 Sites in the United States, March 23-May 12, 2020

Fiona P. Havers, Carrie Reed, Travis Lim et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1001/jamainternmed.2020.4130>

This cross-sectional study estimates the prevalence of severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 antibodies in convenience samples from 10 geographic sites in the United States.

November 30, 2020 (Nat Commun)

Development of a multi-antigenic SARS-CoV-2 vaccine candidate using a synthetic poxvirus platform.

Chiuppesi, F., Salazar, M.d., Contreras, H. *et al.*

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-020-19819-1>

Modified Vaccinia Ankara (MVA) is a highly attenuated poxvirus vector that is widely used to develop vaccines for infectious diseases and cancer. The authors constructed a vaccine platform based on a unique three-plasmid system to efficiently generate recombinant MVA vectors from chemically synthesized DNA. They used this vaccine platform to produce fully synthetic MVA (sMVA) vectors co-expressing SARS-CoV-2 spike and nucleocapsid antigens, two immunodominant antigens implicated in protective immunity. They also discuss the effectiveness of these sMVA vectors in antibody development and demonstrate the potential of using this platform to develop a vaccine

September 29, 2020 (WHO Bulletin)

Fangcang shelter hospitals during the COVID-19 epidemic, Wuhan, China

Juan Li, Pei Yuan, Jane Heffernan et al

<https://dx.doi.org/10.2471/BLT.20.258152>

The authors designed models to test the effect of Fangcang shelter hospitals (rapidly-built temporary hospitals) on the control of the epidemic in Wuhan, China. They found that while the designated hospitals saved lives of patients it was the increased hospital-bed capacity of the large number of Fangcang shelter hospitals that helped to eventually stop the COVID-19 epidemic. The authors recommend increasing hospital-bed capacity, especially through temporary hospitals, to isolate groups of people with mild symptoms within an affected region to help curb and eventually stop COVID-19 outbreaks in communities without effective household isolation.

B. Science and Engineering

November 4, 2020 (European Journal of Radiology)

Deep learning analysis provides accurate COVID-19 diagnosis on chest computed tomography

D. Javor, H. Kaplan, A. Kaplan et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejrad.2020.109402>

Novel deep learning derived machine learning (ML) classifier was developed and an open-source dataset consisting of 6868 chest CT images from 418 patients which were split into training and validation subsets. The model achieved an overall accuracy of 0.956 (AUC) on an independent testing dataset of 90 patients.

December 17, 2020 (Environmental Research)

Did anomalous atmospheric circulation favor the spread of COVID-19 in Europe?

A. Sanchez-Lorenzo, J. Vaquero-Martínez, J. Calbó et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2020.110626>

Lorenzo et al show that an unusual persistent anticyclonic situation prevailing in southwestern Europe during February 2020 (i.e. anomalously strong positive phase of the North Atlantic and Arctic Oscillations) could have resulted in favourable conditions in Italy and Spain for a quicker spread of the virus compared with the rest of the European countries. They suggested that the strong atmospheric stability and associated dry conditions may have favoured the virus propagation by droplet and airborne transmission. Later atmospheric circulation conditions in Europe (July 2020) and the U.S. (October 2020) seem to support their hypothesis. Interestingly, they pointed out the atmospheric conditions during the Spanish flu pandemic in 1918 seem to have some similarities with the current COVID-19 pandemic.

November 19, 2020 (International Journal of Information Management)
Information and communication technologies (ICT)-enabled severe moral
communities and how the (Covid19) pandemic might bring new ones
Carlos M. Parra, Manjul Gupta & Patrick Mikalef.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijinfomgt.2020.102271>

In this study, they present an autopoietic social systems model based on Collectively Prevalent Interpretants (CPIs). They adapt this model to represent and exemplify how Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) may have led to severe moral communities and promote increasingly polarized, radicalized and even extremist viewpoints. They also present recommendations for theory and practice which may help in advancing digital resiliency (by empowering individuals and communities to recognize when this happens).

C. Social Sciences, Humanities and Public Policies

November 28, 2020 ([American Journal of Infection Control](#))

Readability, content, and quality of COVID-19 patient education materials from academic medical centers in the United States

Jessica Kruse, Paloma Toledo, Tayler B. Belton.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajic.2020.11.023>

Kruse et al evaluate the readability, content, and quality of web-based patient education materials (PEMs) on COVID-19 from U.S. academic medical centers. Readability of COVID-19 PEMs was calculated using three validated indices. The content was evaluated using a scoring matrix based on materials available on the Center for Disease Control website. The mean readability was above the recommended 6th-grade reading level. This study shows the importance to provide readable patient education materials on COVID-19 to effectively disseminate accurate information and facilitate patients' understanding of the pandemic.

November 17, 2020 ([Best Practice & Research Clinical Anaesthesiology](#))

Economic Impact of COVID-19 Pandemic on Health Care Facilities and Systems: International Perspectives

Alan D. Kaye, Chikezie N. Okeagu, Alex D. Pham et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bpa.2020.11.009>

The World Bank projects that global growth is shrinking by almost 8% with poorer countries feeling most of the impact, and the United Nations projects that it will cost the global economy around 2 trillion dollars in 2020. Overall, a lack of preparedness was a major contributor to the struggles experienced by healthcare facilities around the world. Items such as personal protective equipment (PPE) for healthcare workers, hospital equipment, sanitizing supplies, toilet paper, and water were in short supply. The authors discuss the economic impact of COVID-19 on US and international hospitals, healthcare facilities and surgery.

November 17, 2020 ([International Sociology](#))

Psychology and politics of COVID-19 misinfodemics: Why and how do people believe in misinfodemics?

Sonia Mukhtar

<https://doi.org/10.1177/0268580920948807>

The author reviews COVID-related misinfodemics from articles in PubMed, EMBASE, Google Scholar and Elsevier. She examines the mechanisms, structure, prevalence, predictive factors, effects, responses and potential curtailing strategies of misinfodemics of COVID-19. She shows the relationship with psychological and ideological motivations that have implications for the development of strategies to overcome the negative consequences on public health.

November 3, 2020 (Media International Australia)

The role of government's 'Owned Media' in fostering cultural inclusion: a case study of the NSW Department of Education's online and social media during COVID-19

Lauren Gorfinkel, Tanya Muscat, Sue Ollerhead et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/1329878X20968291>

This article examines how the New South Wales (NSW) Department of Education in Australia, has engaged with key stakeholders at a time when home-school communications have been heavily impacted by COVID-19.

It focuses on how the Department has invited engagement among its culturally and linguistically diverse stakeholders. It gives examples of the practice by the Department and suggestions for further research that may help to reveal best practices for multicultural and multilingual government-stakeholder engagement.

December 15, 2020 (Clinics in Dermatology)

Rescuing Medical Education in Times of COVID-19

Virginia A. Jones, Kayla A. Clark, Carolina Puyana et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clindermatol.2020.12.010>

The COVID pandemic has impacted on medical education affecting career progression and outcomes. The authors assessed the effects of COVID-19 on dermatology clinics, residency education and medical education. They explored recommendations and offered additional suggestions.